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Mind Games: An Investigation into the Response of Irish Engineering Students to a Mindset Intervention

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ABSTRACT

Stanford psychologist Carol Dweck has studied motivation and learning all her career. After 20 years of research, she concluded that a student's mindset was a key determinant of academic success. She divides learners into fixed and growth mindset persons. The fixed mindset person believes that intelligence is a fixed quantity, and so when such a learner encounters failure, they tend to give up, believing that they have reached their natural limits. The growth mindset learner, by contrast, believes that difficulties and failures are essential elements of learning, challenges to be overcome, rather than the end of the learning road. She has written a bestselling book on this, *Mindset: The new psychology of success*. [1]

Not much work has been done on Mindset in Europe, and this project is to investigate if European students behave in similar ways to American students. The research was done with First-year Level 7 students of Mechanical Engineering at TU Dublin. A five-week intervention, following the methodology outlined in Professor Dweck's book was done, with a different Mindset survey given to the students each week. The final week was Professor Dweck's standard Mindset survey, but of the first four weeks, three were taken from Annie Brock's book, *The Mindset Coach* [2] and the fourth from the University of Illinois at Chicago's Maths Department version [3]. Brock's surveys were dichotomous, whereas all the others were Likert scales.

The results show limited success in changing students' mindsets and in correlation between Mindset score and Exam results.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past twenty years, educational psychologists have become aware of the importance of non-cognitive factors on the academic success of students. The

excitement generated by this research stems from the fact that many of these factors are learnt, and if detrimental to learning, can be unlearned.

The term ‘non-cognitive’ is, of course, a misnomer, as all the activity being studied is cognitive, just not traditionally academic. Duralak [4] suggests the phrase ‘social and emotional learning’, but it has proven difficult to shift the long-used term ‘non-cognitive.’

This paper looks at Mindset, developed by Carol Dweck of Stanford University, which claims that people can have either of two mindsets, fixed or growth. A short test indicates into which category a student fits, and if it is the ‘fixed’ category, Dweck has a series of tutorials designed to move them into the growth mindset and improve their learning outcomes.

2.0 BACKGROUND

Educational research is not a straightforward enterprise, mainly due to the multiplicity of factors, from both nature and nurture, which blend together in unpredictable ways, making it difficult, if not impossible to isolate direct causality in research.

The Latin word *educare* means to ‘draw out.’ The role of education is to draw out the natural ability of the child, an ability that is the melding of their genetic heritage (their genotype) and their environment (both shared and non-shared). Behavioral geneticists study this interplay and have come up with some important insights [5].

Everyone knows that some children have an aptitude and a taste for traditional academic work. Both qualities are influenced—but not determined—by genes. These pupils are the easiest for schools to handle, and they tend to do well in the current system. They are also the pupils that selective schools pick out and whose successes are then claimed by the schools to be the result of a superior education. Current policies and the “blank slate” philosophy hold up these children as models. They suggest that if we work harder then all children can be made to fit this mold. As a result, current approaches push non-academic children to become mediocre generalists regardless of their natural abilities, interests, hopes, and dreams.

Studies of reading by behavioural geneticists identifies the genetic component as being somewhere between 60 and 80%. Knowing this, the task of the educator is to use the genes to their best advantage in each case, meaning that education, from primary to tertiary, should be personalized.

2.1 MINDSET

The US psychologist, Carol Dweck [1], identifies two mindsets, fixed and growth. Fixed minds make little effort, relying on their ability. If their ability is not enough, they quit, usually blaming someone or something for their failure.

Growth mindset people know they have to work. They accept failure along the way as a challenge, a lesson, not a reason to give up.

The fixed mindset is easy. You don’t have to do any work, because you either have it or you don’t. If you don’t succeed, it’s not your fault, it’s someone else’s: your teacher, the referee, your boss.

The growth people enjoy working to succeed, enjoying the challenge of getting there.

Malcolm Gladwell [6] put a rough number on the effort hours needed for complete mastery: 10,000. He reckons that’s roughly the hours put in by diverse people, from

a teenage Bill gates on his computer, to the young Beatles in Hamburg. Before their amazing success, there were years of work which moved them up a level from the rest of us.

Dweck has devised an eight-item self-answered survey, with a six-point Likert answer scale with possible responses ranging from 'disagree a lot' to 'agree a lot'.

The key lesson from Dweck's work is that Mindset is acquired, and can be changed. She has devised online workshops to help people make the change from fixed to growth mindsets, and this has resulted in improved academic scores. [1]

3.0 THE HIGHER EDUCATION SECTOR IN IRELAND

Ireland has seven traditional universities, ranging from the oldest, Trinity College, Dublin (TCD, founded in 1592) to the newest, NUI Maynooth (1997). Then there is the Technological University, Dublin which was created from a merger of the Dublin Institute of Technology, and the smaller Institutes of technology at Blanchardstown and Tallaght. TU Dublin is a member of the European Universities Association, with degree awarding powers to doctorate level. There remain ten Institutes of Technology, some of which are in the process of becoming Technological Universities. There are also small private colleges and other independent colleges.

Admission to higher education in Ireland is via a State body, the Central Admissions Office (CAO). Access to programmes is allocated on the basis of points obtained in the State Leaving Certificate examination (maximum attainable points were 600 over a range of six subjects, and are now 625 with a bonus for passing the higher level mathematics exams). Qualifications are graded according to a scheme devised by the National Qualifications Authority of Ireland (NQAI). In this scheme, Level 7 is an Ordinary bachelor degree, Level 8 is an Honours bachelor degree, Level 9 is a master's degree and Level 10 is a doctorate.

In this group, TU Dublin has perhaps the most interesting history, having grown organically from a late 19th century group of technical colleges that dealt mainly with craft education, into a degree level institute – initially with degrees awarded by TCD. Since 1993, DIT has been a fully independent institution with degree-awarding powers, covering the full-range of higher education courses, from Level 6 certificates all the way to Level 10 doctorates. It is now Ireland's first Technological University.

3.1 THE TU Dublin LEVEL 7 ENGINEERING STUDENT BODY

The first-year students of Mechanical Engineering in TU Dublin constitute an above average (for level-7 nationally) group of students, with Leaving Certificate entry points typically around 350 (out a maximum possible of 625). In the Academic year 2018-19, the number of students was 60, with an average of 354 points. It is also worth mentioning the overwhelming male bias of the that class, with only seven female students on the course in that year.

4.0 METHODOLOGY

In the physical sciences, theory is verified, or falsified, by laboratory experiments. Even in Psychology, which deals with the more complex and multi-faceted subject of human beings, it is possible to devise empirical experiments to test various theories. Walter Mischel's famous Marshmallow test, first done at Stanford in the early 1960s measured children's self-control by how long they could resist a marshmallow, given the promise of a second one if they waited. [7]

In educational research, it is rarely possible to do such tests, both on grounds of scale and expense. Instead, the researcher is reduced to devising surveys, and hoping that students will take them seriously enough to answer honestly. This paper relies on surveys using standard instruments developed by psychologists over many decades, and tested on tens of thousands of students, mainly in the United States. An important difference between Europe and the United States is that students are usually paid for completing surveys, and this does improve participation and completion rates.

Even with good quality instruments, there are still some issues:

1. Only those who attend can answer, making university surveys quite different from primary and secondary level where attendance is legally compulsory.
2. The surveys are voluntary, so only those motivated will answer.
3. The central tendency problem, where bored responders answer 3 for most 5-item Likert surveys.
4. Longitudinal surveys are particularly problematic, as the subset who respond are never the same from survey to survey. This was clear with this intervention, which was spread over five weeks, and only 11 students did all 5 surveys.
5. The questions are standard instruments developed by psychologists. The language can be confusing for young students, e.g. words such as ‘diligent’, ‘aloof’, not normally a part of a teenager’s vocabulary. This is even more true for non-native speakers of English.
6. Some questions in Carol Dweck’s Mindset survey are, in our opinion, ambiguous. For example, ‘I like my work best when I can do it really well without too much trouble’ is evidence of a healthy attitude to work/life balance, not of a closed mindset. And ‘I like my work best when I can do it perfectly without any mistakes’ is a reasonable position to hold, and not necessarily evidence of a closed mindset.

5.0 METHODS

The Mindset intervention in Semester 2 of 2018-19, consisted of two parts: a twenty-minute presentation on Mindset, followed by a short survey. The first week was introductory, mainly focusing on a TED talk given by Carol Dweck on Mindset, with a 10-question Likert survey on Fixed and Growth Mindsets. [2]

The second week had a more detailed presentation on the fixed and growth Mindsets, and the ways in which each is present in everyone. It was followed by a 10-question dichotomous survey. [2]

The third week focused on how the brain operates, its different parts, but especially the way in which new neural pathways grow when new intellectual tasks are undertaken. This was followed by a 20-question Likert survey from the University of Illinois [3].

The fourth week tackled the issue of individual responsibility for learning, in what Carol Dweck terms her SMART scheme:

Specific — Write a specific description of your growth-mindset goal

Measurable — Write how you plan to track progress toward the goal

Actionable — Write specific steps you can take toward attaining your goal

Realistic — Write what resources and supports you need to achieve the goal

Timely — Write your deadline for achieving your goal.

This was followed by a shorter 8-question dichotomous survey on Fixed and Growth Mindsets, with the balance shifted 5/3 in favour of Growth questions. [2]

Week five examined the historical context of intelligence measurements, beginning with Alfred Binet’s work on IQ and finishing with James Flynn’s [12] discovery of the growth of IQ scores per decade, due to the transition from simple and concrete rural societies of the late 19th Century to the more complex, and abstract, urban world of the late 20th Century and early 21st Century. It was emphasised that the Flynn effect is positive evidence of the Growth hypothesis, that undertaking more complicated tasks requires the human brain.

It was followed by Carol Dweck’s standard 8-question Likert survey on Fixed and Growth Mindsets [1].

6.0 RESULTS

The average score in the Dweck Mindset survey was 32.29. Dweck categorises this as G1, and describes such a person as follows: ‘You are unsure about whether you can change your intelligence. You care about your performance and you also want to learn, but you don’t really want to have to work too hard for it’ (Mindset Works® EducatorKit - Module 1 Toolkit). This corresponds to the average Mindset score from the previous academic year, 2018-19, which was 30.66, and is also in Dweck’s category G1.

As the five surveys have different numbers of questions, ranging from 8 to 20, and are both dichotomous and Likert, it was decided for each survey to calculate the total percentage fixed and growth component, based on the maximum possible score in each category. This allows for comparisons to be made between the different surveys.

Table 1: Student Scores from the Five Mindset Surveys

	W1 Fixed	W1 Growth	W2 Fixed	W2 Growth	W3 20-point Likert	W4 Fixed	W4 Growth	W5 Dweck Likert
n	27	27	24	24	23	19	19	24
Mean	14.81	20.11	1.16	4.16	41.82	0.63	4.89	32.29
SD	4.61	2.69	1.09	0.76	6.99	0.76	0.32	5.88
Adjusted Mean %	59.25	80.44	23.33	83.33	69.71	21.05	97.89	67.27

7.0 ANALYSIS

In week 1, on average 59% selected the fixed statement as true. By week 2, this had dropped to 23%, and to 21% by week 4.

Conversely, the percentage of students who selected the growth statement as true was 80%, 83% in week 2, and 98% in week 4.

The Likert surveys in weeks 1 and 5 were compared for the 11 students who did all 5 surveys. As week 1 had a 1 to 5 option, and week 5 had a 1 to 6 option, the data in week 1 was adjusted using the following linear transformation [9]:

$$Y = \frac{(B-A)(x-a)}{(b-a)+A} \tag{1}$$

Where a is the original minimum (1) and b the original maximum (5), A is the new minimum (1) and B the new maximum (6).

The week one data was also scaled up by 2.67 to match the higher number of questions in week 5 (8 versus 5). The two means were then compared using a two-tailed Mann-Whitney U Test for non-parametric data.

The result was $p = 0.2627$, with a z-Value of -1.116 .

There is therefore no difference in the Likert scores in week 1 and 5.

Two things seem clear from the data: firstly, the Likert scores show no effect from the intervention, and indeed are little different from the previous year's class, who had no intervention.

Secondly, the dichotomous scores do show a consistent trend of improvement over the course of the intervention.

Perhaps because of the central tendency inherent in Likert scales, the presence of a neutral option makes it difficult to see how the Likert survey can be used to track the efficacy of the intervention.

At the end of the year, the students average mark across all modules was plotted against their Mindset score from Week 3.

The R-squared value was 0.0099, indicating almost no correlation.

Figure 1: Plot of Exam Scores at Year End 2019 v Mindset Scores from W3

This might seem as if the intervention did not achieve anything, but it is well to remember that the fruits of education may take a long time to appear. The Mindset intervention does give students some ideas about how learning works, and so might benefit them in their life-long learning experience.

8.0 CONCLUSION

This is very much a preliminary work, and as they (probably) say in France, *une hirondelle ne fait pas le printemps!*

However, it is interesting, even with a small amount of data, that the effect of an intervention can result in clear changes in Mindset scores, as shown in dichotomous surveys, but not in the Likert surveys.

Carol Dweck claims great things for Mindset intervention, for example in her 2013 paper [10], she said a single class Mindset intervention, delivered over the web, improved the failure rate by 7% compared to a control group who had no intervention. It should be borne in mind, however, that Dweck has a commercial interest in Mindset interventions, as she sells her Brainology software to thousands of secondary schools

Others are not so sure. Brooke Macnamara, Assistant Professor of Psychology at Case Western Reserve University, finds little evidence to support her claims: *'School officials, policymakers and other stakeholders may want to think twice before they buy a growth mindset intervention product or dedicate part of their curriculum to teaching growth mindsets thinking it's going to make a difference in children's academic performance. Our research suggests there is a good chance it won't.'* [11]

It is over one hundred years since Alfred Binet produced the first standardised IQ test. Binet was motivated to create the test to identify weak students, so that they could be given extra teaching, to bring them up to the standard.

Binet's insight that intelligence is malleable has been shown in recent years by the American psychologist, James R. Flynn. In his 2009 book [12], *What is intelligence*, he discusses what is now known as the Flynn Effect, the massive rise in average IQ scores over the 20th Century. As Asbury and Plomin discovered as geneticists, genes determine that which is constant, environment that which is variable. Education will have succeeded when the only variation between students is genetic, not environmental. The challenge for educators is to so personalize students' education so that that goal can be achieved. A short Mindset intervention could be a simple, but effective, part of that process.

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